

Thorium Triethanolamine as a New Chelating Material and an Anion-exchanger

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A new chelating ion-exchanger thorium triethanolamine has been synthesised which shows anion-exchange properties as well. Nitrogen atom present in the amine group offers the sites for the chelation with metal ions. The exchanger exhibits anion character at high pH values. Its anion-exchange capacity, sorption capacity, chemical stability, composition, heat treatment, ir spectra, breakthrough capacity, potentiometric titrations and rate of exchange have been determined. Distribution coefficients of 21 anions and 18 cations have been determined. Owing to the large differences in their K_d values many analytically important separations of cations and anions have been achieved.

THE chelate ion-exchangers have drawn attention recently. However, the possibility has not been explored towards inorganic chelate ion-exchangers. Sn^{IV} -diethanolamine¹, a cation exchanger, and hydroxides of Sn^{IV} ², Zn^{IV} ³, Al^{III} ⁴ and others^{5,6} behaving as anion-exchanger, lack in the stability in basic solutions. To overcome these limitations efforts were made for a chelating ion-exchanger exhibiting amphoteric character. The exchanger prepared by incorporating triethanolamine group into the matrix of thorium oxide was not only stable in basic media but important separations of anions and cations were also successfully achieved.

Experimental

A SICO electrically temperature controlled shaker, a Bausch and Lomb spectronic 20 instrument and a Elico Li-10 pH meter were used.

Thorium nitrate (B.D.H.) and triethanolamine (E. Merck) were used and the other chemicals were of A.R. grade.

Thorium triethanolamine : A 0.1 M solution of thorium nitrate and a 0.1 M solution of triethanolamine solution were mixed in 1:4 ratio. The resulting precipitate was allowed to stand for 24 h at room temperature (25–30°), then washed with deionised water, filtered and dried in air for 3 h. The exchanger particles were converted into hydroxyl form by keeping in 2M NaOH solution overnight, intermittently replacing the supernatant liquid with a fresh NaOH solution, and finely washed with deionised water and dried at 40°.

Anion-exchange capacity : The ion-exchanger (1 g) was converted in the desired form (chloride, bromide, iodide, thiocyanate, thiosulphate, sulphate) by treating with 2 M solutions of sodium/potassium/ammonium salts of different anions. The exchanger was placed in the column with glass-wool support.

The column was washed with deionised water thoroughly. A 1.0 M sodium nitrate solution was used as an eluent. The elution rate was maintained at 0.5 ml min⁻¹.

Sorption capacity : The sorption capacity for copper was determined by column operation using 1 g exchanger. A 0.5 M EDTA solution was used as an eluent for copper ions sorbed by the exchanger. The eluents were collected in 10 ml fractions. Each fraction was treated with perchloric acid and nitric acid to decompose EDTA, followed by the addition of sodium acetate solution. The solution was then titrated against 0.01 M EDTA. The sorption capacity of thorium triethanolamine exchanger for copper(II) ions was found to be 0.71 meq g⁻¹.

Chemical stability : The chemical stability of thorium triethanolamine sample was determined by shaking the exchanger (0.5 g) for 4 h in respective solutions in which its dissolution was to be checked. The amount of thorium was determined in the supernatant liquid by titrating against 0.02 M solution of EDTA while triethanolamine was determined spectrophotometrically by ninhydrin⁷.

To check the stability in EDTA solution, the exchanger (1 g) was shaken with 0.02 M EDTA solution (20 ml) for 6 h. The exchanger was slightly soluble, i.e. 0.09 mg Th/g sample.

Composition : Thorium triethanolamine (500 mg) was dissolved in aqua regia (25 ml) and diluted to 100 ml in a standard flask with deionised water. The amounts of thorium and triethanolamine were determined titrimetrically using Cu-pan indicator and spectrophotometrically by ninhydrin, respectively.

Heat treatment : Thorium triethanolamine sample was heated at different temperatures in a muffle furnace for 2 h. The anion-exchange capacity for thiocyanate ion was the determined by column

operation method. The capacity at 40, 60, 100, 150, 200 and 300° was found to be 0.61, 0.60, 0.46, 0.38, 0.34 and 0.30, respectively.

Structural studies: For characterisation of the exchanger, IR spectra (KBr) of thorium triethanolamine were taken using KBr.

Breakthrough capacity: The breakthrough capacity was determined by column operation. Solution of copper nitrate (12.60 mg/10 ml) was passed through a column loaded with thorium triethanolamine (1 g) on a glass-wool support. The amount of copper(II) collected in each 10 ml fraction was determined. The results are plotted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Breakthrough curve.

Potentiometric titration: The pH titrations of thorium triethanolamine (0.5 g) were performed with solution of hydrochloric acid, sulphuric acid and nitric acid with their respective salts using the method of Topp and Pepper⁶. pH of the solution after shaking for 4 h was noted. The results are plotted in Fig. 2.

Distribution coefficients: The distribution studies for anions and cations were carried out by batch process. The K_d values for anions in deionised water and different molar solutions of NH_4OH were calculated.

Separations: On the basis of large differences in distribution coefficient values, a number of separations were tried. Thorium triethanolamine in nitrate form (2 g) was taken in a glass column (30 cm \times 0.69 cm). The solution containing known amounts of anions to be separated was passed twice through the column at a very slow rate to allow complete sorption of the anions. 10 ml fractions of the eluate were collected and the amount present in each fraction was determined by standard methods. The same procedure was applied for the separation of cations.

Fig. 2. pH titration curves of thorium triethanolamine.

Rate: The rate was determined by batch process. Thiocyanate (0.20 milliequivalent) was shaken with thorium triethanolamine (0.5 g) at different intervals of time. The amount of thiocyanate remaining in the solution was then determined. The results are plotted in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Rate of adsorption of thiocyanate ions.

Results and Discussion

The present exchanger possesses a good anion-exchange capacity in the range 0.80–0.18 (Table 1). It is, therefore, likely that the incorporated triethanolamine group acquires a free charge on its nitrogen atom and is responsible for the anion-exchange behaviour of the material.

It is worth mentioning that thorium triethanolamine does not exist in H^+ -form. However, the exchanger possesses appreciable sorption capacity. The metal ions were taken up by the exchanger and

TABLE 1—ANION-EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF THORIUM TRIETHANOLAMINE

Sl. no.	Anions	Salt used	Capacity meq. g ⁻¹
1.	Chloride	Sodium chloride	0.80
2.	Bromide	Sodium bromide	0.59
3.	Iodide	Potassium iodide	0.44
4.	Sulphate	Sodium sulphate	0.25
5.	Thiosulphate	Sodium thiosulphate	0.18
6.	Thiocyanate	Ammonium thiocyanate	0.61

eluted with EDTA solution. That thorium triethanolamine does not show any hydrogen liberation capacity may be related to the possibility that there is no fixed negative charge with the exchanger matrix. The sorption of the metal ions took place due to the presence of nitrogen atom of amine group that offers sites for the chelation with the metal ions. The exchanger acquiring the colour of the sorbed metal ions can be conspicuously seen.

Thorium triethanolamine exchanger is quite stable in organic and neutral aqueous solutions. The material shows dissolution in strong acidic media, hence it should be avoided. A 1 M solution of sodium hydroxide or ammonium hydroxide may, however, be safely used.

Exchange capacity of thorium triethanolamine decreases with the increase in drying temperature. This should be used as anion-exchanger at temperatures below 100°.

The ir spectra of thorium triethanolamine reveal the following bands: 3 300–3 500 (OH), 1 770–1 780 w (C–O), 1 600–1 620 (C–C), 1 020–1 220 (C–N bend), 1 370–1 480 sbr (CH bend) and 800 cm⁻¹ (Th–O).

It is clear from the above observation that the exchanger still retains the amine moiety. Chemical analyses show 1 : 3 ratio of thorium and triethanolamine in the exchanger. Breakthrough capacity Cu^{II} (Fig. 1) is such that upto 40 ml it can be safely passed through 1 g exchanger. pH-metric titrations (Fig. 2) indicates that thorium triethanolamine in its hydroxyl form behaves as mono-functional anion-exchanger. The analytical utility of thorium triethanolamine can be observed from its amphoteric behaviour. The distribution behaviour of different anions are generally high. K_d values were appreciably lowered when a solution of NH₄OH was used for equilibrium studies. A decrease in K_d values is observed with the increase in the concentration of ammonium hydroxide. Many separations were achieved on the basis of large difference in K_d values of various anions and cations in different solvent systems (Tables 2 and 3). The separations were quantitative and the errors within admissible range.

TABLE 2—SEPARATIONS OF ANIONS ON THORIUM TRIETHANOLAMINE COLUMN

Sl. no.	Mixture	Eluent NH ₄ OH	Eluate ml	Amount loaded mg	Amount found mg	Error %
1.	CrO ₄ ²⁻ Br ⁻	0.10 M	100	7.70	6.60	2.40
		0.01 M	90	3.01	2.94	2.32
2.	Cr ₂ O ₇ ²⁻ Br ⁻	0.10 M	100	4.68	4.57	2.35
		0.01 M	90	3.01	2.97	1.92
3.	SO ₄ ²⁻ I ⁻	0.10 M	90	1.33	1.30	2.25
		0.01 M	90	2.90	2.82	2.75
4.	S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻ Pr ⁻	0.10 M	110	5.39	5.35	0.74
		0.01 M	90	3.01	2.97	0.99
5.	SO ₄ ²⁻ Br ⁻	0.10 M	70	1.34	1.30	2.98
		0.01 M	90	3.01	2.94	1.99
6.	Cr ₂ O ₇ ²⁻ I ⁻	0.10 M	100	4.69	4.61	1.70
		0.01 M	90	2.90	2.86	1.37
7.	CrO ₄ ²⁻ I ⁻	0.10 M	100	7.07	6.99	1.13
		0.01 M	90	2.90	2.82	2.75

TABLE 3—SEPARATIONS OF CATIONS ON THORIUM TRIETHANOLAMINE COLUMN

Sl. no.	Mixture	Eluent	Eluate ml	Amount loaded mg	Amount found mg	Error %
1.	Cu ⁺⁺ Mg ⁺⁺	0.01 M EDTA	90	0.70	0.68	2.80
		Deionised water	80	0.31	0.30	3.20
2.	Co ⁺⁺ Mg ⁺⁺	0.01 M EDTA	100	0.77	0.76	1.30
		Deionised water	80	0.31	0.30	3.20
3.	Pb ⁺⁺ Ba ⁺⁺	0.01 M EDTA	90	2.07	2.04	1.40
		Deionised water	110	0.66	0.65	1.50
4.	Cu ⁺⁺ Sr ⁺⁺	0.01 M EDTA	100	0.70	0.69	1.40
		Deionised water	100	1.31	1.30	0.76
5.	Pb ⁺⁺ Mg ⁺⁺	0.01 M EDTA	90	2.07	2.02	2.40
		Deionised water	90	0.31	0.30	3.20
6.	Pb ⁺⁺ Sr ⁺⁺	0.01 M EDTA	90	2.07	2.04	1.40
		Deionised water	100	1.31	1.30	0.76

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References

1. A. SUGGI, N. OGAWA and H. HASHIZUME, *Talanta*, 1979, **26**, 189.
2. P. VERMON and K. M. NYO, *Sep. Sci. Technol.*, 1978, **13**, 273.
3. J. N. KING and J. S. FRITZ, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1978, **153**, 507.
4. R. J. PHILLIPS and J. S. FRITZ, *Anal. Chem.*, 1978, **50**, 1504.
5. Z. HUBICKI, H. HUBICKA and S. TUSIAK, *Mater. Sci.*, 1977, **3**, 53.
6. F. VERNON and H. ECKLES, *Anal. Chm. Acta*, 1975, **79**, 239.
7. F. D. SNELL and O. T. SNELL, "Colorimetric Methods of Analysis", 3rd. ed., Van Nostrand, Princeton, 1954, Vol. IV, 37.
8. N. E. TOPP and K. W. PEPPER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 3299.